

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. The article describes the important aspects of organizing foreign language classes with the help of modern information and communication, pedagogical technologies, electronic textbooks and multimedia tools, as well as methods for using these tools and their effectiveness.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, electronic textbook, multimedia, explanation-illustration, reproductive, problematic, research teaching methods.

Аннотация. В статье описаны важные аспекты организации занятий по иностранному языку с помощью современных информационно-коммуникационных, педагогических технологий, электронных учебников и мультимедийных средств, а также методы использования этих средств и их эффективность.

ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии, электронный учебник, мультимедиа, объяснение-иллюстрация, репродуктивная, проблемная, исследовательская методика обучения.

To fundamentally improve the quality of education in the educational institutions of our republic, to widely introduce modern information and communication and pedagogical technologies, electronic textbooks and multimedia tools into the educational process, to equip the educational and laboratory base with the most modern educational and laboratory equipment, computers special attention is being paid to strengthening with techniques, as well as forming an effective system of material and moral stimulation of teachers' hard work.

The state educational standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system lists the goals and tasks of the subject, according to which the main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the education of students. It is emphasized that it is the formation of communicative competence in a foreign language in order to carry out activities in daily, scientific and professional spheres in the civilized world. Today, one of the main requirements for a high professional qualification is the perfect knowledge of foreign languages. It is not for nothing that special attention is paid to learning English, which is the leading language of international communication. Teaching and learning of foreign languages in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is rising to a new level of quality based on the scientific approach and the introduction of new information-communication and pedagogical technologies that fully meet the requirements of the time.

Which foreign languages are studied in the country depends on many factors. The political, economic, cultural and social potential of the country and its relations at the international level, as well as the degree of connection to the regional and global network, as the first foreign language in the process of learning foreign languages, are often considered the most important language according to the "usefulness criterion". It is known that the expression of thinking, communication between peoples, spiritual and other communication is manifested through language.

Therefore, in the process of up to higher education, in the process of developing the technology of teaching additional texts in English and implementing the principles of creating professional programs for this purpose, special attention should be paid to every scientific research aimed at in-depth study of foreign languages. This means defining the conceptual framework in advance in the program being modeled. The technology of teaching professional supplementary texts in English to the educational system before higher education can be considered as one side of the issues of the implementation of the above-mentioned tasks. It is important to ensure the priority of the educational system in the processes of training specialists, including the introduction of new technology-mechanisms of teaching foreign languages.

The reflection of such technologies in the educational system will increase the level of foreign language teaching and help to form reading skills in foreign languages, including English. We need to create a network methodology for determining the future needs of those who have mastered the English language

(this is done in accordance with the Classifier, qualified descriptions and the State Education Standard). Harmonization of education and training and their interdependence, ensuring consistency in the training of specialists who have mastered the English language in the continuous education system, introducing effective forms and methods, new additional texts teaching technology methodology and extensive use of other advanced teaching methods is a guarantee of positive results. Based on the fields of study of specialists, the use of additional text technology in the process of English language teaching increases the language learning opportunities of future specialists. It is also possible to use alternative methods, that is, to meet the demand for pupils and students by adopting alternative methods in the education system of other countries, it is advisable to use all the above-mentioned approaches to prediction in various combinations. The terms of relations in a foreign language, speech, additional professional texts show that knowledge of many types of learning is the demand of the times. Without denigrating the essence of other languages, especially when communicating in English, understanding speech, reading and writing, practice of speech activity, reading wide-ranging and professional literature on specialization, specialization, explanatory annotations, theses, as well as in the process of exchanging written information. the importance of information and communication technologies is clearly demonstrated and defined. As noted by our Methodist scientists, students should express the content of the text in an image, express the reality reflected in the text, the opinion of the characters participating in it, as well as their opinions as an addition to the topic of the conversation, the student's vocabulary will help you to think correctly in English. If this method is used correctly in the educational process, it will be possible to achieve positive results both in terms of mastering, in

terms of teaching periods, and in perfect learning of the English language. The use of additional text programs focused on the educational process is one of the methodical approaches that provide a good opportunity to adequately solve the problem of English language teaching. Approaches to teaching based on such a methodology are now widely spread in the national methodology. All these approaches are not pure, but used in various combinations. It is important to mention that such an approach in English language teaching should not be neglected, because it is possible to solve a number of educational issues more successfully than other technologies due to the technology of this approach. Using computer equipment and smart technologies for the development of speech in English language classes in vocational colleges, it becomes easier to receive information and text content on the basis of various programs.

Based on the nature of the additional text, it is suggested to write down or recite the composition created by means of various game-based educational language learning programs on the computer, or with the help of pre-extracted pictures. It's important to use things like creating a situation and then narrating that composition. Also, having a conversation about parts of the text or content in the text is useful for the development of speech. In this way, opportunities are created for students to expand their vocabulary and participate in research activities in order to apply the knowledge they have acquired. Additional text topics can be prepared using the press, periodicals, mass media materials. Students will be interested in texts about interesting research and scientific discoveries.

If there are some words or expressions in the text that are difficult to understand, it is necessary to consider some simplified examples that help the students to understand them. As a result of such activities, students will have the opportunity to apply the knowledge they have acquired, to expand their scope of knowledge, and to participate in the research process. The most gratifying part is that in addition to language learning, students become more interested in using modern information and communication technologies and the Internet.

Development and progress can be achieved only when new ideas and technologies are used in teaching English. There is no doubt that if they are followed during training, it will have a good effect. The purpose of using additional text teaching technology is to introduce students to the most general ideas in education. This technology reflects a person-oriented approach, effective, positive results can be achieved only if each student acquires knowledge, skills and abilities, but also takes into account the individual characteristics of his development. Exercises designed to check the understanding of the read additional text can be expressed as follows: Answer the questions on the text Tashkent. Some of the questions can be simplified when used to check that the text read from the question-and-answer exercises has been mastered. Teaching additional text in special rooms, in order to be really effective, it is necessary to create conditions for students' independent work using a lingophone device in the classroom. Recently, there has been increasing attention to the use of this method in the classroom. Relying on the latest advanced methods, we understand the independent work of students in English language classes as the formation and improvement of their speaking skills, as well as the independent work related to the development of speech skills in a certain order with the given task. Thus, since learning a foreign

language is a requirement of the present time, developing new methods of language learning for the growing young generation based on the "National Personnel Training Program" and recommending them to the study process is an urgent task for scientists and specialists. is one of the issues. In order for our talented young people to become mature specialists in their fields of interest, first of all, it is necessary to have a perfect knowledge of a foreign language, including English. Therefore, introduction of technologies, ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the time are the main tasks of pedagogues-scientists that cannot be delayed. Training and professional development of specialists is also one of the urgent social problems.

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